

ions⁹. The various ligand field parameters, viz. ν_2/ν_1 , $10Dq$, β' , β , β^0 were calculated⁹ and found to be 2.12, 7.61, 1.25 (σ_1/σ_2); 11 780, 10 000, 12 781 cm^{-1} ; 947, 826; 0.975, 0.783 and 2.47, 21.69% for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. All these spectral data and the band positions fit in the range of octahedral complexes, giving tacit support to this geometry.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (D.K.D.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

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Complexes of Bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-aminopyridine with Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury-(II)

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Manuscript received 18 April 1988, revised 28 March 1989,
accepted 10 November 1989

METAL complexes of various Schiff bases derived from 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (vanillin) have been studied^{1,2}. In continuation of our earlier studies³ Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with vanillin-2-aminopyridine (HMBAP) are reported.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

The Schiff base ligand, HMBP (L) was not isolated in solid state³, because on mixing vanillin with 2-aminopyridine the solid was converted to liquid. So, for the preparation of the complexes *in situ* method was adopted.

Preparation of complexes: To an ethanolic solution of vanillin was added an alcoholic solution

of metal halides with constant stirring. To this solution, an ethanolic solution of 2-aminopyridine was added and the solution was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath. The resulting crystals separated out on cooling were filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried under reduced pressure. In all the complexes the metal halides (MX), vanillin and 2-aminopyridine ratio was 1 : 2 : 2. Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} form complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2\text{X}_2]$, whereas Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} form complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2]\text{X}_2$.

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 4000A spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a EM 390 spectrometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by a Gouy balance and molar conductance on a Systronics 303 conductivity bridge. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values (20–24 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes measured in DMF at 25° at a concentration of $10^{-3}M$ suggest that complexes are non-electrolytes⁴. Molar conductivity values (110–122 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes indicate their electrolytic nature⁵. The electrolytic behaviour of the complexes implies that the anions are present outside the coordination sphere. The ir spectra of the free ligand show bands at 1 630 ($\text{CH}=\text{N}$)⁶ and 1 540 cm^{-1} (pyridine ring)⁷; in the complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2\text{X}_2]$ and $[\text{ML}_2]\text{X}_2$, there is a negative shift in both the frequencies by nearly 30 and 45 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen and pyridine nitrogen⁸. The ring stretching vibrations are due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ observed in the region 1 540–1 330 cm^{-1} . The appearance of a new band in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes at 270–280 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{X}}$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ and I).

The ir spectra of the nitrate complexes show bands at ~1 450, ~1 225, ~1 000 and ~950 cm^{-1} , whereas the perchlorate complexes show bands at ~1 270, ~1 130 and ~970 cm^{-1} . These bands unambiguously suggest the presence of coordinated nitrate⁹ and perchlorate¹⁰ anions. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes in DMF supports the presence of the anions in the coordination sphere. The magnetic moment values of complexes are included in Table 1.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes exhibit bands at 9 000, 19 000 and 24 000 cm^{-1} , corresponding to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_2), and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_3). The crystal field parameters ν_3/ν_1 , Dq/B , B , $10Dq$ and β were found to be 2.13, 1.16, 791.66 cm^{-1} , 9175.6 cm^{-1} and 0.70 respectively. The lowering in the value of B (29.31%) from the free-ion value for Co^{II} (1 120 cm^{-1}) suggests covalent nature of bonding. These values are in close accordance

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	N	Halides	
CoL ₂ Cl ₂	Reddish brown	9.23 (9.24)	8.75 (9.77)	11.10 (11.12)	4.88
CoL ₂ Br ₂	Red	8.10 (8.11)	7.05 (7.07)	21.97 (22.00)	4.82
CoL ₂ I ₂	Blue	7.14 (7.18)	6.81 (6.82)	30.90 (30.93)	5.10
CoL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Orange red	9.12 (9.97)	10.00 (10.15)	—	4.98
CoL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Dark red	8.14 (8.25)	7.36 (7.84)	—	4.78
NiL ₂ Cl ₂	Yellowish red	9.19 (9.20)	8.74 (8.78)	11.10 (11.13)	2.83
NiL ₂ Br ₂	Dark red	8.06 (8.07)	7.68 (7.70)	21.98 (22.00)	2.81
NiL ₂ I ₂	Dark red	7.18 (7.15)	6.80 (6.82)	30.91 (30.94)	2.80
NiL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Orange	9.00 (9.19)	10.86 (10.95)	—	2.82
NiL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Red	8.16 (8.23)	7.68 (7.85)	—	2.80
CuL ₂ Cl ₂	Dark green	9.87 (9.88)	8.71 (8.71)	11.03 (11.05)	1.80
CuL ₂ Br ₂	Greyish green	8.66 (8.68)	7.64 (7.65)	21.84 (21.87)	1.80
CuL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Olive green	9.78 (9.87)	9.28 (9.32)	—	1.81
CuL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Greenish yellow	8.84 (8.90)	7.71 (7.79)	—	Dia
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	Dull white	11.00 (11.03)	9.39 (9.45)	11.92 (11.98)	Dia
CdL ₂ Cl ₂	Light yellow	11.54 (11.57)	8.69 (8.75)	11.08 (11.10)	Dia
HgL ₂ Cl ₂	White	27.49 (27.51)	7.64 (7.70)	9.68 (9.76)	Dia

with the spin-free octahedral geometry of the Co^{II} complexes. In the visible spectra of the Ni^{II} complex three bands were obtained at 8 500, 16 000 25 500 cm⁻¹ attributed to transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ respectively. The parameters were found to be 1.88, 1.12, 9954.56 cm⁻¹, 888.8 cm⁻¹ and 0.85 respectively in the above order. The percentage decrease in the Racah parameter value after coordination was found to be 14.53 which is in close accordance with the reported values for an octahedral Ni^{II} complex. The Cu^{II} complexes show a broad asymmetric ligand field at 12 600–12 900 cm⁻¹ characteristic of distorted octahedral stereochemistry with D_{4h} symmetry.

¹H nmr spectra the ligand (in DMF) show a peak at δ 8.3–8.6 due to the azomethine (CH=N) proton¹¹. The signal at δ 5.6 observed in the ligand is due to ArOH (hydroxyl proton). The signal at δ 8.7–9.0 is assignable to aromatic proton attached with nitrogen of pyridine rings¹². Two singlets observed for the azomethine protons, undergo a downfield shift (δ 9.1–9.6) which seems to be due to the coordination of both the azomethine groups in all the metal complexes. Similarly two singlets observed for the protons adjacent to nitrogen atoms in benzene ring, undergo a downfield shift (δ 9.3–9.5), which seems to be due

to the coordination of both nitrogen atoms in all the metal complexes.

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